

OpenWebSearch.eu

“Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search Infrastructure to Support Europe’s Digital Sovereignty”

Deliverable D2.1
The OpenWebSearch WARC
parsing & content analysis library
Version 1.0

Open Web Search

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Preliminaries

i. Project Info

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Project reporting period	1
Project Coordinator	Prof. Dr. Michael Granitzer, University of Passau

ii. Project Partners

Acronym	Partner
UNI PASSAU	University of Passau
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities
RU	Radboud University
WEBIS	Leipzig University
TUGraz	Graz University of Technology
DLR	German Aerospace Center
CERN	CERN
IT4I@VSB	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Associated Partner)
OSF	Open Search Foundation e.V.
A1	A1 Slovenia
SUMA-EV	Suma e.V. (Associated Partner)
CSC	CSC – Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy
NLNET	Stichting NLnet

iii. Deliverable Info

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iv. Deliverable Summary

This document reviews the status of Deliverable D2.1 "The OpenWebSearch WARC parsing and content analysis library" of the OpenWebSearch.eu project, which is supported by the European Commission (EC) under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme under grant agreement GA 101070014. The deliverable is reviewed in comparison to the objectives planned in the proposal, and with respect to how it integrates with other components of the project. The document also outlines the anticipated plans for further development in the second half of the project.

¹ Granitzer, M., Voigt, S., Fathima, N. A., Golasowski, M., Guetl, C., Hecking, T., ... & Zerhoubi, S. (2023). Impact and development of an Open Web Index for open web search. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*. <https://asistdl.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/asi.24818>

v. Document Management

History of Changes

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Draft of Sec. 1 and 3	0.2	13.02.2024	Introduction; Description of pipeline, cluster deployment and LEXIS integration
Pre-Review-Version	1.0	21.02.2024	
Final Version	1.1	27.02.2024	Integrated reviewer feedback

vi. Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s)

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as "Optional".

Name	Role	Action	Date
Arjen P. de Vries	Reviewer	Review	25.02.2024
Michael Granitzer	Project Coordinator	Approve	

vii. Executive Summary

This deliverable reviews five software components developed in Work Package 2 (WP2):

1. Resiliparse: An open-source library for extracting content from web pages that provides a collection of processing tools for robust and fast parsing of web archive data stored in the common WARC file format.²
2. Resilipipe: An open-source software framework that implements a scalable cluster-based web content analysis pipeline for web archive data based on Resiliparse, and that offers the integration of user-defined web content analysis modules implementing a specific interface.
3. Web Content Analysis Modules: A collection of web content analysis module implementations which serve to enrich the Open Web Index with metadata relevant to a search application, such as geolocation information.
4. TIREx: A platform for evaluating software components related to web search and web indexing in a scalable and standardized way. It is used to evaluate the output quality and processing speed of content analyzers.
5. Deployment: A workflow for the LEXIS platform that automates the deployment of Resilipipe configured with specific content analysis modules on OWS.eu data centers to process new web crawls at scale.
6. Usage statistics: As of mid February 2020⁴, the project has processed approximately 1.23B web pages in 185 languages, resulting in a storage of ca. 77 TiB.

The implemented software offers all the necessary prerequisites to achieve the project results as planned.

² The Web ARChive (WARC) file format is used to store crawled web pages:
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/WARC_\(file_format\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/WARC_(file_format)).

1. Introduction

The goal of the OpenWebSearch.eu (OWS.eu) project is to provide a freely accessible and transparent Open Web Index (OWI). For the creation of search engines using the OWI, we aim to build the OWS Engine Hub that provides search technology stacks to compose new vertical search engines. As shown in Figure 1.1 (top green boxes), the OWS Engine Hub as well as custom search user interfaces (UIs) and different web search applications are built, among other things, on top of a web crawling and processing pipeline (orange boxes) that includes the steps (1) web crawling, (2) web crawl pre-processing and indexing (reviewed in this report), and (3) and index post-processing, e.g., to compute embeddings based on large language models (LLMs).

This report focuses on the results of the development of the web crawl pre-processing step, which is based on the scalable open-source software Resiliparse and Resilipipe. Furthermore, we describe the first implemented content analysis modules and its deployment and automated execution in the OWS.eu data centers. We also present the TIREx evaluation platform that was honored with the Best Paper award at the premier scientific venue of the information retrieval community, SIGIR 2023.³ It is used to evaluate the performance of the content analysis modules integrated into Resilipipe.

Figure 1.1: Federated Data Infrastructure

The document is accompanied with the following resources:

Source Code:

- Resiliparse: <https://github.com/chatnoir-eu/chatnoir-resiliparse>
- Resilipipe: <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/preprocessing-pipeline>
- TIREx: <https://github.com/tira-io/ir-experiment-platform>

³ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3539618.3591888>

1.1 Deployment Architecture

Figure 1.2 shows the deployment architecture of the software components of this deliverable, which implement the web crawling and processing pipeline across the OWS.eu data centers. The pipeline is divided into several cluster tiers, where each tier consists of a *well-defined set of services* (and corresponding software stack) that runs on the same cluster computer or set of virtual machines. The figure also outlines the relations between cluster tiers.

Figure 1.2: Overview of Cluster Tiers and Interfaces.

Resilipipe and its dependency Resiliparse are deployed in the Preprocessing & Enrichment Tier (PET). This tier receives the WARC files created by the Crawling Cluster Tier (CCT), processes them to extract metadata and stores its results as Apache Parquet⁴ (referred to as Parquet) files in an S3 Bucket. The Parquet files are then used by the Index and Storage Tier (IST) to create the index files. One PET per data center is instantiated for processing.

The effectiveness and efficiency of content analysis modules is tested in the Preprocessing Plugins Evaluation Tier (PPET) in which TIREx is deployed. TIREx provides the environment to run software in a sandboxed environment to evaluate it on benchmark datasets. Section 4 provides a more detailed overview of TIREx. The PPET needs to be run at only one data center.

⁴ <https://parquet.apache.org/>

1.2 Vision for the Software Components

Resiliparse, Resilipipe, and TIREx are the three main software components of Deliverable D2.1. We envision additional uses for each of them in the remainder of the project as well as beyond it.

1.2.1 Resiliparse

Resiliparse builds the basis for reading and parsing web archive data. It is designed to aid developers in safely processing arbitrary and likely malformed or even malicious web data in a robust, easy, and resource-efficient way.

The library is a tool belt tailored specifically to the needs of developers reading Web Archive (WARC) files and processing the contained HTTP protocol data and HTML payloads. It eliminates boilerplate code and the need for individual third-party libraries by taking into account and automating most recurring tasks that arise when processing WARC files. Resiliparse's default mode is to make as few assumptions about the well-formedness and validity of the data, allowing for easy, safe, and error-free web data processing at scale.

Resiliparse is being developed as a native Python module, making it highly resource-efficient and fast, saving memory and CPU cycles when parsing billions of web documents at scale. The library has already been picked up by the wider open-source community working with web archives beyond the project. One indicator is the activity on GitHub with 38 stars and eight forks, including forks by a researcher at the ScaDS.AI Center for Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence, Germany, and by the Common Crawl Foundation, USA.

1.2.2 Resilipipe

Building on the fast and robust parsing capabilities of Resiliparse, Resilipipe is a framework designed to extract metadata from web crawls in a fast, distributed setting. It comes with a standardized interface for content analyzers and a set of implemented analyzers to perform standard tasks and more advanced tasks of web data processing.

The pipeline features a set of scripts to be deployed on high performance computing (HPC) infrastructures. It is run as an Apache Spark job on the de facto standard HPC setup using SLURM, with the help of the script collection Magpie.⁵ These scripts facilitate the deployment with a range of HPC job schedulers. For instance, we provide corresponding deployment workflows for the LEXIS platform used in the project.

Due to its modular design, the pipeline can be easily extended with additional content analysis modules to fit the requirements of different use cases. We will extend the pipeline during the course of the project both with our own analyzers as well as contributions from project partners and the wider open web search community. As the content analysis library grows, this creates a synergy for the development of new custom vertical search engines.

⁵ <https://github.com/LLNL/magpie/>

1.2.3 TIREx

The integration of new content analysis modules into Resilipe requires their systematic evaluation to ensure sufficient performance in terms of effectiveness and efficiency. This is operationalized in TIREx: The Information Retrieval Experiment Platform. TIREx is a platform to conduct standardized, reproducible, and scalable experiments in the realm of information retrieval. We currently host an instance of TIREx with 15 benchmark corpora (totalling 1.9 billion documents) on which 32 specific retrieval tasks are based, which form the basis for many core search engine components.

New content analysis modules can be evaluated on TIREx by running the dockerized module on a task-specific dataset. Due to the focus of TIREx on standardized and reproducible experiments, this facilitates the selection of the best-performing content analysis implementations for each analysis task. If a module addresses a new task, the developers of that module are asked to provide a suitable benchmark dataset, thus enabling other members of the open search community as well as the information retrieval research community to research, evaluate, and transfer new content analyzers.

The combination of TIREx and Resiliparse/Resilipipe help ensure that any new metadata, that is added, does not negatively affect retrieval effectiveness of systems that consume our preprocessed content but contributes to improving it.

1.3 Statistics

Documents preprocessed: ~ 2.79 Billion (including duplicates) until mid February
Number of unique languages: 185
Terabyte crawled and stored: 77.1 TiB

1.3.1 Number of documents

Figure 1.3 shows the development of the number of documents crawled starting in August 2023, which have been processed using Resilipipe and Resiliparse. The ten most frequently occurring languages are visualized separately. By February 17th 2024, a total of 2.79 billion documents have been crawled and processed. These numbers are before applying deduplication.

From the end of October until the end of November 2023, the crawling and preprocessing pipeline were able to run without interruption on both the Karolina cluster at IT4I and the Linux cluster at LRZ. The data before that time is drawn entirely from IT4I (data collected at LRZ was lost due to hardware complications). By mid of November, IT4I provisioned a new S3 endpoint to expand the storage, which required crawling activities to pause until the new endpoint was properly integrated. In addition to that, crawling was stopped for some time in December to upscale the Crawling Frontier. Starting on February 6th, the project partners at CERN started updating the OpenSearch Instance, leading to a pause in crawling activity since then.

Figure 1.3: Number of Documents per Language.

2. The Resiliparse Library

The first and central component of our software components is Resiliparse, an open-source web archive processing library. This section gives a brief overview of Resiliparse and its state of development.

2.1 General Overview

The parsing of web data requires both high efficiency to be able to process large amounts of data as well as robustness to handle the diversity of documents on the web. Resiliparse provides both of these features as a native Python module. The library is written largely in native C and C++ using Cython, as well as plain Python code. Several core components are being ported to standalone Rust modules to provide better memory safety guarantees and to make them reusable also outside the Python ecosystem.

The Resiliparse code and development process adhere to modern standards of safe software design and the code comes with a comprehensive test suite covering around 90% of the lines of code (LOC). Furthermore, the public API is extensively documented with descriptions of all methods and parameters as well as usage examples and tutorials.⁶

2.2 Architectural Overview and Modules

Resiliparse consists of two main modules: the FastWARC library and the Resiliparse core data processing framework. The former is a standalone library for reading and writing WARC files that can also be used without the rest of the Resiliparse suite, and the latter is a set of tools for processing and parsing web data.

2.2.1 FastWARC

The FastWARC library is designed as a faster and more efficient alternative to existing WARC parsing libraries. The library allows reading and writing of WARC/1.0 and WARC/1.1 files without the processing overhead incurred by existing alternatives such as warcio. FastWARC supports uncompressed WARC files as well as gzip- and lz4-compressed archives. Support for the newer WARC specification draft for zstd-compressed archives is envisioned for future implementation.

2.2.2 Resiliparse Core

The Resiliparse core library provides tools for the processing of web data, either from WARC files (using FastWARC) or other sources. The library eases and automates standard tasks that developers face frequently while parsing arbitrary web data.

The main processing and extraction features at this point are:

- Reliable character encoding detection based on the existing chardet library and safe conversion from arbitrary encodings to Unicode.
- Fast detection of several common MIME types.
- Basic but very fast language detection with guarantees for fixed-memory consumption and linear processing time.
- Fast and efficient HTML parsing and DOM processing based on the open-source Lxml HTML5 parser engine.

⁶ <https://resiliparse.chatnoir.eu/en/stable/>

- A rule-based plaintext and main content extractor to extract relevant textual data from websites.
- A set of helpers for stream processing from unreliable sources (such as processing WARC files from a remote network location) with automatic retry logic and error management.
- Processing guards to help keep processing jobs within set memory and time limits in order to reduce the occurrence of out-of-memory errors or stragglers in large batch jobs.

With this initial set of features, the Resiliparse core library implements convenient solutions for many basic needs of developers processing web data or other textual batch data efficiently and robustly at scale. By providing a unified bundle of (existing and new) tools for many basic tasks, it boasts robustness of processing pipelines and reduces boilerplate code and the need to reinvent the wheel for every new batch or stream-processing job.

2.3 Evaluation of Resiliparse

The extraction of main content and text from websites is an active subject of research. Therefore, we tested our current implementation against competing approaches in a peer-reviewed study.⁷ Figure 2.1 gives an overview on the ability of different content extractors to identify the main content from both low as well as high-complexity websites. A website's complexity depends on the boilerplate usage as that makes it more difficult to extract the main content.

Figure 2.1: ROUGE-LSum F1 Scores for different Content Extractors

We used the ROUGE-LSum F1-score to measure the lexical overlap between a website's main content and the extraction results and found Resiliparse to be competitive with other extractors. At the same time, Resiliparse is an order of magnitude faster than other solutions, making it well-suited for the processing of large amounts of web data.

⁷ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3539618.3591920>

3. Resilipipe

With Resilipe, we implement a framework that enables scalable cluster-based web content analysis for web archive data based on Resiliparse. In our deployment architecture (see Section 1.1), Resilipipe is deployed in the Preprocessing & Enrichment Tier (PET) to parse WARC files produced by the Crawling Cluster Tier (CCT), extract relevant metadata and output the results as Parquet files for the Index and Storage Tier (IST).

3.1 Content Analysis

In addition to a website's plain text, there is a range of useful metadata that can be obtained to improve the user experience of search engines. This includes data that influences the relevance scores of a web page with respect to a specific search query and user, like the language of a page or geographical locations it refers to. Another example is the genre category such as news, health, business, or science, that allows to partition the index into smaller chunks and thus make it easier to be handled by search engines that focus on a specific genre of content. Finally, several types of technical metadata such as the MIME type, Microdata, or JSON Linked Data can be used to index the website's content more accurately or allow search engines to present information beyond the standard list of results.

The extraction of all metadata happens in the Resilipipe preprocessing pipeline.⁸ This subsection describes the content analysis for a single WARC file, the operationalization and cluster deployment of this process for many WARC files at scale is described in the following section.

Each WARC file contains a number of records, with each record holding the data about a single web page. For all records, we obtain the basic information listed below:

- MIME type
- URL components
- Elements from the WARC and HTTP headers.
- A category label if its domain is among those curated by the Curlie.org community⁹

If the web page's MIME type is a form of text, we gather more data:

- Plain text using Resiliparse's main content extraction
- Language based on Resiliparse's language detection or information from the web page

The majority of records has the MIME type "text/html" and is processed more extensively. For these web pages, we collect the following information directly:

- Microdata and JSON Linked Data
- Links to images, videos or other websites

The processing of HTML records can be expanded in a modular fashion with additional content analyzers. In order to enable both other parties in the project consortium as well as third parties to develop their own content analysis modules, we provide an interface definition as an abstract class that content analyzers have to implement. This ensures both a simpler process for developers of modules by having a clear orientation as well as a good integration with the rest of the pipeline. We already verified this process by integrating a prototype of the geoparsing module that project partner DLR is currently developing as part of Task 2.5.

⁸ <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/preprocessing-pipeline>.

⁹ Refer to <https://curlie.org/docs/en/about.html> for more information.

A central concern when integrating external modules is to ensure their effectiveness and efficiency at the task they were developed for. This quality assurance is performed in a systematic way on TIREx, our experimentation platform for information retrieval. TIREx is described in more detail in Section 4.

3.2 Cluster Deployment

This section outlines the deployment of Resilipipe on a High Performance Computing (HPC) infrastructure. As content analysis is conducted individually on each WARC file, the process is well-suited for parallelization with Apache Spark. In order to increase the degree of automation and the integration between the preprocessing and the indexing step, we make use of the LEXIS platform.

3.2.1 Deployment with Apache Spark

Apache Spark is an open-source framework for running processes in parallel on a cluster computer. We use the Python API PySpark to perform the content analysis steps described above on the WARC files created by the crawling tier CCT. The full process is illustrated in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Illustration of the parallelization of the preprocessing pipeline using Apache Spark.

When submitting a new preprocessing job on one of the clusters, the first step consists of counting the number of WARC files to be processed for the current specification. This number is used to dynamically estimate the number of nodes required to complete the job in a specified time and request the necessary resources using the cluster's job scheduling system. Slurm is the scheduler of choice on both IT4I's Karolina cluster and LRZ's Linux cluster. However, as we use the open-source script collection Magpie for our deployment, it can be easily adapted to other job scheduling systems such as Lustre, Moab, or Torque.¹⁰

After receiving the node allocations, Magpie is used to create a Spark cluster on the HPC infrastructure. Finally, the preprocessing job in PySpark is submitted to this cluster to perform the content analysis and write the extracted metadata as Parquet files to the S3 storage.

¹⁰ Magpie's script collection can be found under <https://github.com/LLNL/magpie/>.

3.2.2 Automation using LEXIS

The distribution of a large amount of data across different data centers in Europe requires a unified approach for processing and accessing it. In addition to that, the deployment of the Preprocessing & Enrichment Tier (PET) on a HPC infrastructure needs to be handled in a standardized, highly automated way. Finally, we want to facilitate third party access to the index files created by our activities.

To achieve these goals, we use the LEXIS Platform¹¹ which is maintained by our project partners IT4I and the LRZ. The LEXIS platform has been built by the LEXIS project whose activities were supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.¹²

The core idea behind LEXIS is to provide easy access to HPC resources of different supercomputing centers. It allows users to define workflows that can be run automatically across HPC systems in Europe and also enables a secure management of large amounts of data between data centers.

The communication between HPC system and client is realized by the HEAppE framework, which manages information about jobs and data on the HPC infrastructure and provides functions for job management, monitoring, and user authentication as well as file transfer and encryption.

In the OpenWebSearch.eu project, we currently work on defining LEXIS workflows for the automatic end-to-end execution of the PET. Additionally, LEXIS will manage third party access to the index files of the OWI and allow users to download the specific partitions of the index relevant to their use case.

3.3 Current Operational Status

At the time of reporting, Resilipipe is deployed at two clusters of the project: IT4I's Karolina cluster and LRZ's Linux cluster. Following the cluster tier logic, the deployments use the respective S3 endpoint at the respective data center to access the WARC files created by the CCT and save the Parquet files containing the metadata.

The crawls are processed on a daily basis at both locations. In January, we processed an average of 3,577 WARC files per day in the PET at IT4I and 1,259 files at LRZ. Each WARC file contained an average of 3,276 documents and took 2.19 seconds to process with the current selection of content analysis modules.

The implementation of LEXIS workflows is ongoing and we are optimistic to complete them in the coming weeks. Once this step is completed, the preprocessing and indexing pipelines can be run in an automated end-to-end setting to continuously produce index files.

For illustration purposes, a Resilipipe deployment is also available as a Docker image.¹³ When provided with a local directory of WARC files, it can be run to produce Parquet with the contained metadata. This is especially useful for quick prototyping and is currently applied by Work Package 4 (WP4) to develop first search applications.

¹¹ <https://lexis-project.eu/web/lexis-platform/>

¹² Grant Agreement No. 825532

¹³ <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/preprocessing-pipeline#docker-image>

4. TIREx

TIREx, The Information Retrieval Experiment platform, is a platform for evaluating software components related to web search and web indexing in a scalable and standardized way. It is deployed in the Preprocessing Plugins Evaluation Tier (PPET) to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of content analyzers. Our research on TIREx was honored with the Best Paper award at the SIGIR 2023 conference on information retrieval.¹⁴

Our evaluations are conducted in a two-fold fashion: First, a new content analyzer is evaluated in an isolated setting on its dedicated task using the TIRA Integrated Research Architecture (TIRA).¹⁵ Second, the analyzer is integrated into an end-to-end retrieval pipeline and evaluated in this setup using TIREx.¹⁶ In addition to the outline of TIREx, we describe our ongoing efforts to invite the community to contribute content analyzers.

4.1 Evaluation Process and Versioning

All evaluations on TIREx and TIRA are conducted by packaging the software as a Docker image. In order to facilitate the process for contributors of new software, we developed GitHub/GitLab Actions that build Docker images directly from git repositories and upload them to TIREx with tracking metadata such as the commit hash and branch. In addition to reducing the effort for developers, this also substantially improves experiment reproducibility as each result can be traced back to the exact version of the software that produced it.

The robustness of the Github/Gitlab Actions was already verified in three events that collected submissions to TIRA/TIREx. It was used in the IRIXYS'23 workshop described in Section 4.3 as well as by two university courses that used TIREx submissions as part of their information retrieval courses.

4.2 Intrinsic and Extrinsic Evaluation TIRA / TIREx

Preprocessing can be applied at different stages of the retrieval pipeline and work on both documents and user queries. Some preprocessing steps for documents must be aligned with their counterparts for queries, such as lemmatization, stopword removal, or sparse indexing with SPLADE.¹⁷ Steps like Spam classification, document expansion, or geoparsing, on the other hand, can be performed independently for documents. In order to reflect this circumstance in our evaluation efforts, we organize preprocessing software into three different types: (1) document preprocessing, (2) query preprocessing, and (3) query-document preprocessing. We evaluate each software using intrinsic evaluations in TIRA and extrinsic evaluations in complete retrieval pipelines using TIREx.

For the intrinsic evaluation, we use benchmark datasets with a specific focus of the task of the software. Examples include Spam classification evaluated with F1 score, main content extraction evaluated with ROUGE score or BERTScore between the extracted main content and the ground truth.

The extrinsic evaluation is conducted by combining multiple components into a complete retrieval pipeline and evaluating end-to-end retrieval effectiveness. If, for instance, a Spam classifier would filter out a substantial subset of all relevant documents, we can quantify the effect of that module on the overall ranking in addition to its intrinsic evaluation score.

¹⁴ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3539618.3591888>

¹⁵ <https://www.tira.io/>

¹⁶ <https://www.tira.io/tirex>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/naver/splade>

4.3 Community Involvement and Scientific Workshops

A central goal for TIREx is to foster the development of new content analyzers and retrieval components. Therefore, we organize hackathons and workshops to invite the scientific and open-source community to contribute and evaluate software in an open and collaborative way.

Two recent examples of these activities are the 2023 edition of the International Research & Innovation Centre on Digital Intelligent Systems workshop¹⁸ (IRIXYS'23) and the first Workshop on Open Web Search¹⁹ (WOWS'24) at ECIR 2024.

At IRIXYS'23, four international teams submitted a total of 31 web page classification modules that classified if a given web page is Spam, adult, or benign content. The software was submitted as code and dockerized using the aforementioned Github/Gitlab Actions. In order to ensure a close connection to the OWS.eu project, the software was evaluated on samples of the Open Web Search Crawl as well as the ClueWeb09 and the ClueWeb12 corpora.²⁰

The WOWS'24 workshop encourages participants to submit a diverse set of content analysis modules with the aim of combining them in novel ways as a result of the workshop. At the time of writing, six teams have already submitted components ranging from document preprocessing to document expansion and reduction with SPLADE to genre classifiers.

In addition to the information retrieval community, we encourage students to participate in the workshop. In this regard, we conduct a one week hackathon together with the TU Dresden in which four student teams develop content analysis modules with support by members of the OWS.eu project team. This hackathon is part of the teaching activities at TU Dresden and students receive credits for their participation.

¹⁸ <https://irixys.uni-passau.de/workshops-summer-schools/>

¹⁹ <https://opensearchfoundation.org/wows2024/>

²⁰ <https://lemurproject.org/components.php>

5. Conclusion and Outlook

This report summarizes our work on the different software components enabling the large scale preprocessing of web crawls. As the first component, the Resiliparse library builds the basis for parsing the WARC files created by the crawling activities. It allows us to safely process web data and handle even malicious content. Our research showed that Resiliparse's main content extraction is on a competitive level with alternative solutions while being faster by an order of magnitude.

With Resilipipe, we deploy Resiliparse on the HPC clusters of our project partners and conduct the extraction of metadata in a fast, distributed way. Resilipipe comes with a set of basic content analyzers that can be extended in a modular fashion. By providing an interface for the development of content analysis modules, we facilitate the development of new software as well as the adaptation of Resilipipe to different demands. For the automation of Resilipipe, we currently develop a workflow on the LEXIS platform. Upon completion, this increases the interconnection between the preprocessing and indexing steps.

In order to systematically evaluate new content analysis modules, we use our experiment platform TIREx. It allows software developers to easily run their modules in a dockerized setting and evaluate them both on the specific task they were developed for as well as in the context of an end-to-end retrieval pipeline. TIREx has already proven itself in scientific workshops and information retrieval education. By lowering the barrier for reproducible experiments, we support the development of high quality content analysis modules by the open web search community.

In future work, we plan to conduct further research on different forms of content analysis with a particular focus on computational ethics, the information nutrition label, and argument mining. Examples include the detection of textual content that can be disturbing to certain audiences or the identification of arguments in the text of web pages.

6. Appendix

6.1 List of Acronyms

Acronym or Abbreviation	Term
CCT	Crawling Cluster Tier
DEM	Demonstrator
DG Connect	European Commission Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
HORIZON-RIA	Horizon - Research and Innovation Action
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IST	Index and Storage Tier
OWI	Open Web Index
OWLer	Open Web Search Crawler
OWS or OWS.eu	OpenWebSearch.eu project
PET	Preprocessing and Enrichment Tier
PPET	Preprocessing Plugins Evaluation Tier
RIA	Research and Innovations Action
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WARC	Web Archive Fileformat